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LEADERSHIP STYLES AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE: A REVIEW

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Abstract

In today's competitive business environment, organizations are under great pressures facing multifarious challenges. Under these conditions, it has become very much crucial for organizations to differentiate themselves in the eyes of demanding customers for their long run survival and better performance. Literature suggests that it is the effective leadership which is the life blood for the survival of an organization and in making a perceptible difference in it. Thus, during the past several decades the impact of leadership on performance has become an area of interest among researchers and practitioners working in the area of leadership. The present study is, therefore, an attempt to critically examine the existing literature highlighting the relationship between these two constructs.

Key Words: Leadership, Organizational Performance, MLQ.

Introduction:-

In today's competitive business environment, organizations are under great pressures and are facing immense challenges. Under these conditions, it has become very much crucial for them to differentiate themselves in the eyes of demanding customers for their sustainable survival and better performance. Several authors argued that it is the effective leadership which is the life blood for the survival of an organization and in making a perceptible difference in it (Bass, 1990; Bruke & Day, 1986; Clark & Campbell, 1992). Thus, during the past several decades the impact of leadership on performance has become an area of interest among researchers and practitioners working in the area of leadership

(Cannella and Rowe, 1995; Giambatista, 2004; Rowe *et al.*, 2005). Scholars like Zhu *et al* (2005) viewed leadership as one of the key driving forces for improving firms' performance. Similarly, Dimma (1989) believes that leadership is undoubtedly the critical determinant of the success of an organization and thus determines organizational performance in the competitive global market. Bass (1990) even goes further and argued that leadership is the single most critical factor in the success or failure of an Institution.

Despite the widespread acknowledgment of the importance and value of leadership and increased research into the leadership-performance relationship, major gaps still remain unabated in our understanding. The present study is, therefore, an attempt to critically examine the existing literature highlighting the relationship between these two constructs.

Leadership-performance link: A historical overview

Like many other organizational studies, the root of leadership-performance link can be traced back to trait studies on leadership which concentrated on identifying the personality traits which characterized successful leaders (Argyris, 1955; Mohoney *et al*, 1960). These theorists further argued that successful leaders are born with some innate qualities to improve organizations performance (Stodgill, 1948) Subsequent researches however argued that it is the behaviour and style of leaders that has a bearing on the success of organizations (Hemphill & Coons, 1957; Likert 1961). However, scholars like Fielder 1967; House 1971; Vroom & Yetton, 1974 shift the emphasis away from 'the one best way to lead' to 'context sensitive leadership'. However, in recent years, researchers began to refocus on 'one best way of leadership' by giving emphasis to visionary and charismatic leadership. Also recent studies on leadership have contrasted 'transactional leadership' with 'transformational leadership'

Although the above review indicates that research into leadership has gone through periods of scepticism, yet it can be asserted that leadership acts as a defining element in the success or failure of organizations. In this context, therefore, the effective leadership is the life-blood for the survival of an organisation and in making a perceptible difference in it (Bass, 1990; Burke & Day, 1986; Clark, & Campbell, 1992). As has been rightly asserted by some management analysts, the basic difference between successful and unsuccessful organisation is its leadership. Schultz (1982) for example, asserts that half of all new businesses fail within first two years and only a third survive five years and in most cases poor leadership causes the failure. And, as per Katz and Kahn (1978) organisations leaders are major determinants of its success or failure. Further, the styles of leadership adapted is considered by some other researchers (e.g Awamleh,1999; Yammarino *et al* 1993) to be particularly important in achieving Organizational goals and in evoking performance among subordinates (Barling *et al*, 1996; Berson *et al*, 2001; Zacharatos *et al* 2000).

Similarly, today's business management attributes its successes to the leadership efficiency i.e the leadership styles of administrative supervisors which have a considerable effect on Organizational Performance (Terry 1960). Also, effective leadership is seen as a potent source of management development and sustained competitive advantage for organizational performance improvement (Avolio, 1999; Lado *et. al*, 1992; Rowe, 2001). Scholars like Zhu *et al.*, (2005) viewed leadership as one of the key driving forces for improving a firm's performance. Fiedler (1996), one of the most respected researchers on leadership, even goes further to assert that the very success of a group, organization, or even an entire country depends upon the effectiveness of a leader. Many other scholars as Sun (2002) compared the leadership styles with the leadership performance in schools and enterprises, and found that leadership styles has a significantly positive correlation with the organizational performance in both schools and enterprises. Others also presented that executive leadership is statistically linked to firm performance (Hart & Quinn, 1993). Furthermore, empirical analysis of businesses' financial performance has found the CEO's influence 15 percent of the total variation in financial performance (Nohria, Joce, & Roberson, 2003). There are researchers who believe that in the modern business environment, more adaptive, flexible styles of leadership are needed for modern organizations to be successful (Bass & Avolio, 1993;

Bass, Avolio, Jung, & Berson, 2003). However, in the past, some researchers have argued that the actual influence of leaders on organizational outcomes is overrated and romanticized as a result of biased attributions about leaders (Meindl & Ehrlich, 1987). Similarly, House and Aditya (1997) also criticised leadership studies for focussing excessively on superior-subordinate relationships to the exclusion of several functions that leader perform, and to the exclusion of Organizational and environmental variables that are crucial to mediate the leadership-performance relationship. For example, House and Aditya (1997) distinguished micro-level research and macro-level research which is supported by other researchers as well who argued that leaders and their leadership styles influence both their subordinates and Organizational outcomes (Tarabishy, Solomon, Fernald and Sashkin, 2005). Recently, Fenwick and Gayle (2008), in their study of the Missing links in understanding the relationship between Leadership and Organizational Performance conclude that despite a hypothesized leadership-performance relationship suggested by some researchers, current findings are inconclusive and difficult to interpret.

From this review of related literature, it is evident that although some scholars believe that leadership enhances organizational performance while others contradict this, different concepts of leadership have been employed in different studies, making direct comparisons virtually impossible. Gaps and unanswered questions remain. The present study is, therefore, an attempt to critically examine the existing literature highlighting the relationship between these two constructs and, thus, contribute meaningfully to the body of growing literature and knowledge in this area of study.

Leadership-Performance link: empirical evidences

Over the past several decades, the impact of Leadership Styles on Organizational Performance has been a topic of interest among academics and Practitioners working in the area of Leadership (Cannella & Rowe, 1995; Giambatista, 2004; Rowe et al, 2005). However, empirical studies into the link between leadership and Performance have been lacking.

One of the earliest detailed study examining the impact of leadership on performance has been conducted in the context of Icelandic fishing ships by Thorlindson (1987) in which the author revealed that it were the leadership skills of the captains of the ship that lead to 35- 49 percent variance in the performance of different fishing ships.

Ogbanna and Harris (2000) also carried an out a study on areas of organizational culture, leadership and organizational performance involving nearly 1000 companies in U.K. They found that the associations between leadership style studied and performance were all mediated by some form of organizational culture that was present. Leadership style was not directly linked to performance but was merely indirectly associated to it.

The mediating role of Organizational Culture between Leadership and Performance has also been supported by Xenikou and Simoso (2006) who conducted a study on 'Organizational culture and transformational leadership as predictors of business unit performance in the context of Greece. In this study, about 300 employees of a large financial organisation in Greece filled in a number of questionnaires measuring organizational culture orientations and transformational leadership. The results showed that transformational leadership was indirectly and positively linked to performance via achievement orientation. Xenikou and Simoso (2006) argued that these results show that Organizational Culture mediates the effect of Transformational leaders on Performance.

The relationship between Leadership and Culture was also examined by Jaharuddin (2003) in Malaysian context by involving 74 local and 60 foreign companies in Malaysia. The results showed that leadership styles have no influence on organizational performance. In other words, leadership and organizational performance are independent of each other.

Similarly, Hancott (2005) conducted a research on the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational performance in the top 100 companies in Canada. The leaders and senior managers of the top 100 companies in Canada were studied. The study had mixed results with no significant relationship found between the total CEO Transformational Leadership and Organizational Performance measured by five year stock Price change. However, there were significant relationship found between two of the individual sub-scales of Transformational Leadership (Inspiration motivation and Intellectual stimulation) and Organizational Performance measured by stock price changes when tenure was the control variable. CEOs tenure greater than or equal to five years play a role in Organizational Performance based on the findings of the study.

Wang, Jen, Ling (2010), also analysed the relationship between leadership styles and organisational performance by including HRM as a third variable in the model. This study viewed 246 valid questionnaires sent to the corporate owners, executors and operators of Kaohsiung's Nanzi Export processing zone in Taiwan. To measure leadership styles they used variables as charismatic, transactional, transformational, visionary and cultural-based leadership. To measure organizational performance variables used were sales growth, net-income growth, ROI, Productivity, business performance and organisational effectiveness (degree of innovativeness, market share, and staff-turnover). It was found that charismatic, transformational and visionary of the leadership styles are positively related to organisational performance.

In the same way, one of the researches was conducted by Hernandez, (2010) on the relationship between leadership styles and performance in hospitals. Primary data for this research were collected from 109 hospital leaders via MLQ Form 5X. Results from this study indicated an increased likelihood of performance success with the application of transformational characteristics.

More recently, Obiwuru, Okwu, Akpa, Nwankwere (2011) analysed the Effects of leadership styles on organizational performance in Nigeria. The result showed that while transactional leadership style had significant positive effect on performance, transformational leadership style had positive but insignificant effect on performance. The study concluded that transactional leadership style was more appropriate in inducing performance in small scale enterprises than transformational leadership style.

Concluding Remarks and Research Implications:-

In this paper we have examined and reviewed some of the research conducted on the link between Leadership and Organizational Performance. Even though we presented a wide variety of studies, the results are mixed and inconclusive.

Firstly, it is assumed that Leadership is directly linked to performance but the studies conducted by Ogbanna and Harris (2000) and Xenikou and Simoso (2006) shows the opposite. They found that Leadership-Performance link is mediated by form of Organizational Culture that is present. More specifically, Leadership is not directly linked to performance but is merely indirectly associated to it.

Also except for a few studies (Thorlindon, 1987; Wang, Jen, Ling, 2010; Hernandez, 2010) all other studies failed to find the link between these two constructs (eg Hancott 2005, Jaharuddin, 2003 etc). Besides, different concepts of Leadership have been employed in different studies, making direct comparisons difficult. Additionally, many scholars (Hancott 2005; Wang, Jen, Ling, 2010; Bass, 1985) have focused on a limited range of leadership paradigms (e.g transactional and visionary). Classical and Organic paradigms have been omitted when researching the leadership- performance relationship. Thus, there remain some gaps and unanswered questions. So there is a need to re-examine the proposed Leadership-Performance relationship.

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